

Use of Indian Traditional Medicines During Pregnancy, at Labour and for Post Partum

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Indian traditional legacy shows the significant use of plant medicines during pregnancy, child birth and in post partum care in different regions of India. Many herbal plants such as sage, golden cotula, anise, peppermint and cumin etc. are used in pregnancy. To minimise the adverse effects the use of Indian traditional medicines can be the best possible alternatives. These medicines are known to have numerous advantages that can be helpful during or after pregnancy raising mil production, reducing nausea, easing labour pain reducing morning sickness or reducing flatulence. However, clinical trials must be conducted to determine the taking of herbal medicines. It is seen that there is a research gap and lack of regulatory framework regarding the use of herbal medicines.

This paper aims to highlight the most common traditional Indian remedies used by pregnant woman along with their uses.